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ICT Access and Women Empowerment: Rural-Urban Divide

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Abstract

At present, the increasing penetration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) has transformed the dynamics of women's empowerment across rural and urban settings. Thus, the study aims to explore the role of ICT Access, Digital Skills, and ICT Usage in influencing women's empowerment, with a particular focus on the rural-urban divide in the Jangalmahal region. The study used stratified random sampling technique for sample selection and applied survey method to collect 385 respondent's data. Empowerment index was developed using PCA method while considering all the six dimensions of the empowerment variables. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, correlation analysis, multiple regression models, and moderation analysis were employed to analyze the data using Python software. The results showcase that ICT Access, Digital Skills, and ICT Usage have a significant positive impact on women empowerment. However, there is no statistical significant difference observed in overall empowerment between rural and urban women. The regression outcome indicated that Digital Skills and ICT Usage were more critical in rural areas, whereas ICT Access played a stronger role in urban areas. Moderation analysis confirmed that Area Type significantly influences the strength of the relations between ICT variables and empowerment outcomes. From the analysis, it can be said that there is need for tailored strategies to foster digital inclusion. In the rural context, infrastructural provisions must be complemented by skill-building initiatives. The study provides several theoretical and practical implications such as the study advances theoretical understanding of ICT-enabled empowerment and provides recommendations for policymakers aiming to bridge the gendered digital divide and promote inclusive development.

Keywords: ICT Access, ICT Usages, Women's Empowerment, Rural-Urban Divide, Digital Skills

1.0 Introduction

Nowadays, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have an important role on reshaping socio-economic landscapes around the world (Roztock et al., 2019; Zheng et al., 2018). The global ICT market was estimated US\$367.67 billion in 2023 and expected to reach US\$577.93 billion in 2028 at a CAGR of 9.47% (Global Data, 2024). The ICT plays a crucial role in education, employment, health, and political participation (Shirazi et al., 2010). Despite the significant transformative potential in the society, ICTs access and usages are still not evenly distributed through region and geographic contexts (Pick & Nishida, 2015; Salemin et al., 2017). Women, especially those living in rural areas, often face greater barriers to ICT access than their urban counterparts, thereby exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities (Novo-Corti et al., 2014; Townsend et al., 2013). Bridging this divide is essential not only for achieving gender equity but also for fostering inclusive and sustainable development.

Women's empowerment, broadly defined as the process through which women gain the necessary resources, agency, and voice to make strategic life choices, has increasingly been linked to both access to and effective utilization of information and communication technologies (ICTs) (Kabeer, 1991; Mosedale, 2005). These technologies provide essential tools for enhancing economic participation, educational attainment, political engagement, and personal autonomy, thereby expanding women's opportunities (Lechman & Popowska, 2020). However, empirical evidence indicates that rural women often encounter compounded challenges, including limited infrastructure, lower digital literacy, financial constraints, and socio-cultural norms that inhibit their ability to access and benefit from ICT innovations (Aruleba & Jere, 2022). The global focus on women's empowerment as a means to achieve gender equality is underscored by Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5) (Leal Filho et al., 2023; Wonde, 2024). To meet their SDG targets, governments are prioritizing the empowerment of women as a pathway to gender equality. This is particularly crucial in developing and underdeveloped countries, such as India, where women's participation in the workforce remains significantly low. Numerous studies have highlighted the disparities in women's empowerment between rural and urban areas.

Acknowledging the significance of this critical issue, the present study primarily intended to explore the interrelations between ICT access and women's empowerment in both rural and urban contexts. The study provides several significant findings by addressing the rural and urban context

regarding women empowerment. Furthermore, it offers empirical evidence that can guide policymakers, development practitioners, and community organizations in designing targeted interventions to enhance women's digital inclusion and, consequently, their broader socio-economic empowerment. In doing so, the study contributes to ongoing discussions surrounding the Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Gender Equality). This study consists of literature review and theoretical framework, methodology of research, findings and analysis from survey, conclusion and contribution of the study in the following order.

2.0 Literature review

Presently, scholars have provided attention to the relations between ICTs access and women's empowerment. Mobile technologies, internet, and such digital services are considered as key enablers for improving women's capabilities, providing access to information, facilitating entrepreneurial activities, improving education, and enabling participation in political and civic life. In this section, we reviewed the scholarly works and presented it in two subsections.

2.1 ICT and Women's Empowerment

There are several studies highlights that ICTs play a crucial role in different types of women's empowerment and contributed significantly in SDG achievement (Corneliussen, 2021; Verma et al., 2022). Numerous scholars show that ICT plays a crucial role in economic empowerment by providing women with access to knowledge, resources, and markets (Tang, 2022; Pradhan et al., 2021). It facilitates business collaborations, funding opportunities, and enhances networking, which are essential for entrepreneurship (Ogundana et al., 2021). By leveraging ICT, women can improve their business ventures, gain competence, and strengthen their economic status. Patil et al. (2023) highlights that ICT's accessibility and omnipresence empower women in developing areas, ultimately enhancing their lifestyle and promoting entrepreneurship.

The personal empowerment of women receives substantial support from ICT usage by offering digital platforms for independent information access, develop personal network, and self-empowerment activities (Suseno & Abbott, 2021). Studies confirm that information communication technology platforms allow women to develop self-confidence while gaining freedom to choose which leads to personal life control (Alhassan & Adam, 2021; Felgueira et al., 2024).

ICTs through social media and online platforms and communication tools empower social connections which women use to communicate with people who may be beyond their traditional social reach (Mackey & Petrucka, 2021). Digital technologies improve social connection between women while helping them to build stronger community relationships (Suseno & Abbott, 2021; Santos et al., 2023).

Educational empowerment functions as a powerful outcome since ICTs enable learning facilities which enhance women's knowledge and qualifications through e-learning systems and information databases (Stromquist, 2015). Gilbert (2008) showed that the use of ICTs helps to eliminate gaps in knowledge specifically among women who reside in rural areas of marginalized regions.

Through ICT technologies, psychological empowerment develops as women gain better access to healthcare information along with counseling assistance and social networks (Mano, 2014). The digital tools provide psychological benefits that include higher self-esteem and reduced sensitivity stigma in crucial issues (such as reproductive health) but also lead to better emotional health (Rodríguez-Rivas et al., 2022; Naslund & Deng, 2021).

The use of ICTs increases women's political empowerment through gaining civic education knowledge and promoting activism on digital platforms and active participation in political discussions. Digital media tools provide women with superior access to policy dialogues and rights advocacy as well as governance procedures compared to regular communication systems (Nemer & Tsikerdekis, 2017).

People need security empowerment even more in the digital period (Monsees, 2020). Through ICTs, women gain access to emergency services together with legal information and safety applications which improve their protection capacity while extending their feeling of security against violence and abuse. The combination of mobile tools with online reporting systems created additional protection capabilities for women (Cardoso et al., 2019).

2.2 The Rural-Urban Digital Divide

Verma et al. (2022) highlighted that improving ICT access and bridging digital divide can significantly influence women's empowerment. Significant research emphasizes the rural-urban digital divide as a key obstacle to universal ICT access (Acilar & Sæbø, 2023). Infrastructure limitations, including inconsistent power supply, inadequate network coverage, and the high cost

of devices and data plans, disproportionately impact rural residents (Bond, 1999). In addition, rural women are often confronted with multiple disadvantages of limited education, deep-seated patriarchal norms, and reduced mobility, which limit their ability to make optimal use of ICTs (Lay, 2017).

Urban women encounter gender-based obstacles but maintain superior digital infrastructure access and show better digital literacy and more exposure to information communication technology opportunities (Dixon et al., 2014). Empowerment results show a major difference between rural females who reside in urban areas (Biswas & Banu, 2023). Scholars are evident that rural women who possess mobile phones demonstrate fewer skills at utilizing internet access and mobile banking and accessing online government services compared to their metropolitan counterparts (Wyche & Olson, 2018). Thus, the study seeks to examine ICT access and its effect on women empowerment particularly in the rural and urban areas of Jangalmahal region, West Bengal, India.

2.3 Conceptual framework and research hypotheses

The conceptual foundation of this study is grounded in the Technology Empowerment Perspective, which posits that access to and engagement with ICTs can significantly enhance individual agency, participation, and socio-economic outcomes (Johnstone, 2007). Within this framework, ICT Access, Digital Skills, and ICT Usage are conceptualized as key enablers of women's empowerment across personal, economic, social, educational, psychological, political, and security domains.

The availability of ICT facilitates empowerment when it lets women to obtain information and build network connections in digital economy spaces (Dixon et al., 2014). The competencies which allow effective ICT tool and platform utilization known as Digital Skills will amplify women's empowerment capabilities for individual and occupational advancement. ICT Usage determines how frequently women interact with ICT across educational and financial and civic and social activities while positively affecting their empowerment outcomes.

The developed framework establishes Area Type (Rural versus Urban) as a crucial variable which controls how various relations between variables play out. The study expects that rural and urban settings produce different outcomes due to their contrasting infrastructure, socioeconomic and cultural elements which potentially shape ICT-driven empowerment strength and characteristics. Empowerment shows more positive development through ICT Access and Usage in urban areas

since these zones possess better infrastructural and social support systems when compared to rural areas.

The proposed research framework thus integrates ICT-related variables with contextual factors to comprehensively examine the dynamics of women's empowerment in a digitally evolving society. The developed research hypotheses are as follows:

H_{1.1}: ICT Access is positively associated with women's empowerment.

H_{1.2}: Digital Skills are positively associated with women's empowerment.

H_{1.3}: ICT Usage is positively associated with women's empowerment.

H_{1.4}: The relations between ICT Access and women's empowerment is moderated by Area Type.

H_{1.5}: The relations between Digital Skills and women's empowerment is moderated by Area Type.

H_{1.6}: The relations between ICT Usage and women's empowerment is moderated by Area Type.

Fig 1: Conceptual framework

Source: The Authors

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The present study adopts a quantitative, survey-based research design to examine the interrelations between ICT access, usages, digital skill and women's empowerment, with a specific focus on the rural-urban divide. Employing primary data collection, the study seeks to quantitatively assess the extent of ICT access, digital skills, and ICT usage among women and analyze their influence on various dimensions of empowerment. A cross-sectional approach was utilized, collecting data at a single point in time to capture prevailing trends and variations across different demographic segments.

3.2 Data Collection

Data for the study were collected through a structured questionnaire survey conducted in the Jangalmahal region. A total of 400 responses were initially gathered, but after data cleaning procedures, including the removal of incomplete and inconsistent entries, 385 valid responses were retained for analysis. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representativeness across key demographic subgroups. Based on a pilot survey, the study adopted a balanced approach by collecting responses equally from four major women groups: students, housewives, working women, and women Self-Help Group (SHG). These groups were selected due to their varying degrees of interaction with ICT tools and their diverse roles in society, which provided a comprehensive perspective on ICT access and usage patterns. Furthermore, responses were balanced between rural and urban populations to minimize potential biases arising from overrepresentation of specific geographical areas. This approach was deemed critical to generating reliable and generalizable insights, as it reduces the likelihood of skewed data driven by a single subgroup's characteristics.

3.3 Sample Description

The final sample consisted of 385 women, distributed across rural and urban areas, and categorized into the four targeted groups. Among the participants, approximately 54% were from rural areas and 46% from urban areas, reflecting a reasonably balanced geographical representation. In terms of occupational classification, the sample comprised students (26.5%), housewives (35.3%), working women (18.4%), and SHG women (19.7%). Regarding educational attainment, a significant proportion of respondents had completed graduation (35.8%) or higher secondary

education (29.1%), with a smaller fraction holding postgraduate qualifications (17.1%) or primary to secondary-level education (18.0%). Most of the participants indicated an income of 1 to 2 lakh INR per annum (40.8%), then higher than 2 lakh INR (37.6%), and lower than 1 lakh INR (21.6%). As for the family setup, a fairly equal split was found, with 52.5% in joint families and 47.5% in nuclear families. Internet use was significantly widespread throughout the sample, with more than 90% having active use of the internet. Patterns of ownership of devices revealed that smartphones were most widely used ICT devices, followed by a mix of laptops and smartphones, and to a lower degree, personal computers and tablets. The composition of this demographic offers a strong and varied framework for studying the research questions.

3.4 Variables Description

The study operationalized several key constructs. ICT access was measured through a series of Likert-scale items evaluating participants' access to ICT devices and connectivity services. Digital skill was assessed by items measuring self-reported competencies in using digital tools and applications. ICT usage captured the frequency and breadth of activities performed using ICTs, including educational, economic, and social engagements. Empowerment was conceptualized across multiple dimensions, including personal, economic, social, educational, psychological, political, and security empowerment. Each dimension was measured using validated multi-item scales. In addition to these primary constructs, demographic variables such as area type (rural or urban), occupation, education level, income, family type, and internet usage status were also collected to enable subgroup analyses and control for potential confounders.

3.5 Data Analysis

Systematic analysis of data was carried out to fulfil the objectives of the study. First, descriptive statistics, such as means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions, were calculated to represent respondent profiles and major variables. Cross-tabulation and Chi-square tests were utilized to analyze differences in patterns of internet usage and access to ICT gadgets between urban and rural women. To compare the general level of empowerment between rural and urban groups, a Shapiro-Wilk test was initially performed to test for normality, which was followed by a Mann-Whitney U test, since the rural subgroup failed the normality assumption.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was then conducted on the seven empowerment dimensions to construct an Empowerment Index, utilizing the first principal component, which explained

approximately 61% of the total variance. Correlation analysis was carried out to examine the bivariate relations between ICT access, digital skill, ICT usage, and the Empowerment Index.

In this study, Multiple Regression Analysis was conducted to find out the impact of ICT usages, Access, and Digital skill on women empowerment. To explore contextual heterogeneity, separate regression models were constructed for rural and urban subgroups. Finally, a moderation analysis was performed by introducing interaction terms between ICT variables and area type to formally test whether the rural-urban divide moderated the relations between ICT access, digital skill, ICT usage, and empowerment. All statistical analyses were conducted using Python software.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

The study followed standard ethical practices for research with human subjects. The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants before including them in the survey. The respondents were promised confidentiality and anonymity of their answers, and participation was entirely voluntary. The research design and procedure for handling data conformed to ethical standards of privacy, protection of data, and respectful treatment of participants.

4.0 Result

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were computed for all major variables to provide an overview of the data characteristics. The mean ICT Access score was 3.49 (SD = 0.64), Digital Skill averaged 3.38 (SD = 0.68), and ICT Usage was 3.58 (SD = 0.62) on a five-point scale. Across empowerment dimensions, Social Empowerment exhibited the highest mean score (M = 3.76, SD = 0.58), followed by Educational Empowerment (M = 3.71, SD = 0.62) and Political Empowerment (M = 3.63, SD = 0.59), while Personal and Economic Empowerment recorded comparatively lower mean scores. These findings suggest a generally moderate level of ICT engagement and empowerment across the sampled population.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
ICT Access	3.49	0.64	1.50	5
Digital Skill	3.38	0.68	1.50	5
ICT Usage	3.58	0.62	1.50	5
Personal Empowerment	3.53	0.71	1.00	5

Economic Empowerment	3.53	0.74	1.00	5
Social Empowerment	3.76	0.58	1.57	5
Educational Empowerment	3.71	0.62	1.80	5
Psychological Empowerment	3.55	0.65	1.00	5
Political Empowerment	3.63	0.59	1.50	5
Security Empowerment	3.65	0.76	1.33	5

4.2 Cross-tabulation and Chi-Square Tests

Chi-square tests were conducted to explore rural-urban differences in ICT usage and gadget ownership. No significant difference was found between rural and urban women in terms of Internet usage ($p = 1.000$), indicating widespread access across regions. However, a significant difference emerged in terms of access to ICT gadgets ($p = 0.0217$), with urban women exhibiting greater diversity in device ownership, particularly in access to laptops alongside smartphones.

Table 3: Chi-Square test between ICT Usage, ICT Gadget Ownership, and area type

Variable	Chi-Square	p-value	Significant Difference
Internet Usage (Yes/No)	1.000	No	
ICT Gadget Ownership	0.022	Yes	

4.3 Construction of Empowerment Index through PCA

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted on the seven empowerment dimensions and resulted in one dominant component explaining 61% of the variance. The first principal component was utilized to build the Empowerment Index, which successfully summarized the multidimensional aspect of women's empowerment in a single continuous variable for further analysis. An Empowerment Index was computed based on the first principal component, which was reverse-scored such that the dimension is such that higher values relate to higher degrees of empowerment. Since, PCA normalizes components about zero, the original Empowerment Index generated scores where smaller values represented higher empowerment, the opposite of common interpretation. In order to preserve conceptual clarity and ensure that greater index values correspond to greater empowerment levels, the Empowerment Index was reversed by multiplying the first principal component by -1. This modification was confirmed by manual checks on individual empowerment dimensions and sample cases from the dataset.

4.4 Rural-Urban Comparison of Empowerment

Before conducting hypothesis testing, we applied normality tests and observed that the index score is non-normally distributed. In this scenario, we adopted a Mann-Whitney U Test which revealed no statistically significant difference in Empowerment Index scores between rural and urban women ($p = 0.0849$). The result indicates that there is no significant difference in the overall empowerment across geographic locations despite contextual differences in access and resources.

Table 4: Mann-Whitney U Test between Area Type and Empowerment Index

Test	Test Statistic	p-value	Significant Difference
Mann-Whitney U Test	21164.0	0.0849	No

4.5 Correlation Analysis

The Pearson correlation analysis result shows that there is a significant correlation between ICT Access ($r = 0.487$), Digital Skill ($r = 0.675$), ICT Usage ($r = 0.576$), and the Empowerment Index. The correlations imply that higher ICT access, skills, and usage are associated with greater empowerment among women.

Table 5: Correlation among the selected variables

Variables	ICT Access	Digital Skill	ICT Usage	Empowerment Index
ICT Access	1			
Digital Skill	0.490	1		
ICT Usage	0.346	0.478	1	
Empowerment Index	0.487	0.675	0.576	1

4.6 Regression Analyses

Multiple regression analysis was done to fulfill the objectives of the study. The full-sample OLS regression model (Model 1, Table 6) revealed that ICT Access ($\beta = 0.448$, $p = 0.001$), Digital Skill ($\beta = 1.385$, $p < 0.001$), and ICT Usage ($\beta = 1.052$, $p < 0.001$) positively and significantly influenced the Empowerment Index, with the model explaining 56.3% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.563$).

Subsample analyses highlights contextual variation. For rural women (Model 2), Digital Skill ($\beta = 1.429$, $p < 0.001$) and ICT Usage ($\beta = 1.194$, $p < 0.001$) were significant predictors, whereas ICT Access was not statistically significant ($p = 0.610$) ($R^2=0.542$). Among urban women (Model 3),

ICT Access ($\beta = 1.557, p < 0.001$), Digital Skill ($\beta = 0.963, p < 0.001$), and ICT Usage ($\beta = 0.651, p = 0.001$) all significantly contributed to empowerment, with a higher R^2 of 0.635.

Table 6: Regression outcomes

Variables	Model 1 (Full Sample)	Model 2 (Rural)	Model 3 (Urban)	Model 4 (Moderator)
ICT Access	0.448** (0.001)	0.079 (0.610)	1.557** (0.000)	0.079 (0.592)
Digital Skill	1.385** (0.000)	1.429** (0.000)	0.963** (0.000)	1.429** (0.000)
ICT Usage	1.052** (0.000)	1.194** (0.000)	0.651** (0.001)	1.194** (0.000)
Area Dummy (Urban=1)	0.286* (0.049)	—	—	-1.483 (0.126)
ICT Access \times Area	—	—	—	1.478** (0.000)
Digital Skill \times Area	—	—	—	-0.467 (0.072)
ICT Usage \times Area	—	—	—	-0.543 (0.004)
R^2	0.563	0.542	0.635	0.590
Adjusted R^2	0.558	0.535	0.629	0.583

Moderation analysis (Model 4) further validated that Area Type moderated the relations between ICT Access and empowerment (interaction $\beta = 1.478, p < 0.001$) and between ICT Usage and empowerment (interaction $\beta = -0.543, p = 0.038$). This suggests that the effects of ICT variables on empowerment differ between rural and urban contexts.

5.0 Discussion

5.1 ICT Access, Skills, Usage, and Women's Empowerment

The findings provide strong empirical evidence that ICT engagement significantly promotes women's empowerment. Thus, H_{1.1}, H_{1.2}, H_{1.3} are accepted. Higher ICT Access, better Digital Skills, and more frequent ICT Usage are each associated with increased empowerment across personal, economic, social, educational, and political domains. These results align with previous studies highlighting ICTs as critical enablers of women's agency and opportunity (Roztocki et al., 2019; Mosedale, 2005).

5.2 Rural-Urban Dynamics in Empowerment

Despite structural and infrastructural disparities, the absence of a significant difference in overall empowerment between rural and urban women highlights the transformative potential of ICTs across diverse contexts. This suggests that when women have access to ICTs and the skills to utilize them, geographic location becomes less determinative of their empowerment outcomes. These results corroborate previous findings where scholars argued that capacity-building efforts are as crucial as infrastructural investments (Salemink et al., 2017; Pick & Nishida, 2015). For rural women, Digital Skills and Usage are critical drivers of empowerment, while Access alone is insufficient. For urban women, Access itself becomes a powerful determinant alongside Skills and Usage. This divergence highlights the need for context-specific policies and it can be recommending that while rural strategies must prioritize building competencies, urban interventions should focus on expanding infrastructure and lowering cost barriers to access.

5.3 Moderating Role of Area Type

The moderation analysis confirms that the relations between ICT factors and empowerment is not uniform across settings. Based on the findings, the study accepted H_{1.4} and H_{1.6} and rejected H_{1.5}. ICT Access exerts a stronger influence on empowerment among urban women, whereas in rural areas, empowerment is more dependent on the ability to skillfully utilize available ICT resources. This finding aligns with the previous studies that effective ICT-driven development requires an understanding of local sociocultural dynamics (Acilar & Sæbø, 2023; Gilbert et al., 2008).

6.0 Conclusion

The present study has examined the nexus between ICT access and women's empowerment in the rural-urban divide context, drawing on primary survey data obtained from the Jangalmahal area. Through the use of a strong analytical framework involving Principal Component Analysis, correlation analysis, regression modeling, and moderation analysis, the study offers in-depth insights into how ICT-related determinants shape different aspects of women's empowerment across geographical contexts.

The findings affirm that ICT Access, Digital Skills, and ICT Usage are significant predictors of women's empowerment. Greater access to ICT tools, higher digital competency, and more frequent engagement with ICT platforms are each associated with enhanced empowerment outcomes, encompassing personal, economic, social, educational, political, and security domains. Importantly, while no significant overall difference in empowerment was observed between rural and urban women; the drivers of empowerment varied contextually. In rural areas, digital skills and the practical usage of ICTs emerged as more critical, whereas in urban areas, access to diverse ICT devices itself played a more prominent role. The moderation analysis further substantiated that the relations between ICT engagement and empowerment is significantly shaped by geographical context, emphasizing the need for differentiated intervention strategies. At last, it can be said that context specific intervention strategy is required to improve ICT adoption to enhance women empowerment and strengthen SDG 5.

7.0 Theoretical and Practical Implications

The study has several theoretical implications. First, the study contributes literature on ICT-driven development by empirically validating the positive relations between ICT engagement and women's empowerment. By identifying the moderating effect of geographical context, the study extends understanding of how ICTs interact with socio-spatial factors to influence empowerment outcomes. It supports the view that access alone is insufficient without corresponding skills and meaningful usage.

The study also presents several practical implications for the policy makers and development authorities. In rural areas, interventions in rural locations need to focus first on teaching women digital skills before they encourage practical use of ICT. However, urban strategies must

concentrate on delivering various ICT devices alongside budget-friendly internet services to the population. Context specific approach should be structured differently to enhance ICT facilities and bridge the rural-urban digital divide efficiently.

8.0 Limitations and Future Scope of the Study

Although the study considered standard methods, the study has some limitations. First, the study used cross-sectional research design which may restrict the causal relations between ICT engagement and empowerment outcomes. Second, the reliance on self-reported data from the respondents may introduce biasness related to social desirability and subjective perception. However, future study can consider longitudinal approach to enhance the result reliability. The study only considered Jangalmahal region but future study can consider broader region to enhance the generalizability of the findings.

9.0 Funding

No specific grant was obtained for this study from any public, private, or nonprofit funding organization.

10. Ethical Approval

The study adhered to strict ethical guidelines. Participants in this study gave their informed consent and participated voluntarily. All responses were anonymous, and no personally identifiable information was gathered. The survey was thoughtfully created to prevent pain, and the data was safely preserved to guarantee participant privacy and confidentiality.

11. Informed Consent

Informed consent was obtained from the all the participants prior to their participation in the study. Clear explanations of the study's objectives, the voluntary nature of involvement, and the participants' freedom to discontinue participation at any moment were given to them. No personally identifiable information was gathered in this study.

12. Author's Contribution

Both authors contributed to the study's data collection and research design conceptualization. The article's initial draft was written by the first author. The data analysis is done by the second author. The second author supervised the final manuscript.

13. Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

14. Data Availability Statement

The dataset used for this study will be available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

15. Acknowledgement

The study is conducted independently without external funding and assistance.

16.0 Declaration

The authors declare that the research paper is original and follows all the ethical standards.

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